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EGYPT'S ENTRY INTO BRICS AND ITS GEOPOLITICAL IMPACT ON THE EURASIAN CHESSBOARD

POLICY BRIEF #12 JANUARY 2024

COUNTRIES & REGIONS: MIDDLE EAST AND NORTH AFRICA

What are the main consequences of Egypt's entry into BRICS? Cairo's entry into the multilateral initiative on January 1st, 2024 represents an agreement with the so-called emerging world. After the troubled Arab Spring, Egypt acquires a new status by becoming a key player in the process of BRICS expansion on the African continent and in the Arab world. Egypt's entry contributes to the country's economic development and its geopolitical projection in the global order because the weight of BRICS in Egyptian foreign trade will be increased, its dependence on the dollar will be reduced, and the grouping's participation in the geopolitics of the Arab World and the Middle East will be expanded.

First of all, BRICS cooperation in Egyptian foreign trade is promising. Egypt is the most populous country in the Arab world, and the third on the African continent, representing an important consumer market in these two regions. Driven by Chinese exports, Egyptian trade with the original BRICS countries constitutes almost a third of its total imports, which will be expanded with the entry of the United Arab Emirates and Saudi Arabia. Regarding exports, the African country's energy capacity, especially in the supply of natural gas and oil, is an important geoeconomic aspect for the BRICS countries.

Furthermore, the interest in reducing dependence on the dollar is another attractive aspect of the Egyptian inflow. Despite the maintenance of reasonable growth rates, the devaluation of the Egyptian pound and the fall in its foreign exchange reserves had a negative impact on its macroeconomy. The country's entry into the BRICS, two years after it entered into the New Development Bank, expands its conditions of access to foreign currencies, representing an alternative to face its domestic difficulties. Cairo will also be able to expand its access to Arab and Chinese investments, in addition to deepening economic and technical cooperation ties with the countries of the grouping.

Finally, Egypt's entry into BRICS expands the grouping's geopolitical participation in the regional politics of the Arab World and the Middle East. Additionally, being one of the protagonists of the ancient Non-Aligned Movement, Egypt has historically been involved in different arenas of debate about the future of the global order in the 20th and 21st centuries. Its strategic position between the Arab world and the African continent contributes to the consolidation of the BRICS presence in both areas, including nations of different statures in Africa, enabling the expansion of influence in a geostrategic space for the circulation of people and products such as the Red Sea and the Suez Canal.

In summary, we discussed that Egypt's entry into BRICS consolidates a long process of seeking partnership diversity. Egypt's participation in the BRICS enlargement process is favorable to the economic interests of the countries of the grouping and of Egypt itself, enhances the construction of a new global financial order based on the reduction of the weight of the dollar, and strengthens Cairo's geopolitical role between the Arab world and the African continent. We consider the invitation to Egypt as a major diplomatic and geopolitical achievement as part of this initiative, expressing the interest of its countries in expanding their participation in main global decisions and diversifying their presence in geostrategic positions of the Eurasian chessboard

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Keywords: Egypt, Arab World, BRICS.

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Policy Briefs are produced in partnership with The International Institute for Geopolitics & Strategy (IIGS/USA), The Centre for Studies on Geopolitics and Foreign Affairs (CENEGRI/Brazil) and Laboratory of Geopolitics, International Relations and Antisystemic Movements (LabGRIMA/Brazil). The IIGS and CENEGRI are independent think tanks non-profit organizations dedicated to geopolitics and international affairs research. The LabGRIMA is affiliated to the Federal University of Pelotas, Brazil.

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How to cite

SANTOS, Mateus. Egypt's entry into BRICS and its geopolitical impact on the Eurasian chessboard. Policy Brief IIGS/Cenegri/Labgrima, v. 2, n. 12, p. 1-4, 2024.

Policy Brief #12 January 2024

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GEOPOLITICAL IMPACT ON THE EURASIAN
CHESSBOARD**

Policy Brief (Boletim de Geopolítica), ISSN 2357-9455

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ISSN 2357-9455

